

Preparation and Properties of Highly Concentrated Sols. Part III. Sols of Zirconium Hydroxide.

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In recent communications, we have investigated the preparation and properties of highly concentrated sols of some metallic hydroxides. In this paper, we are submitting the results obtained with zirconium hydroxide sol. At first we tried to prepare a concentrated sol of zirconium hydroxide by peptising a freshly prepared precipitate of zirconium hydroxide by a solution of zirconium nitrate. A concentrated solution of zirconium nitrate was prepared and drop by drop, ammonium hydroxide was added to it till the precipitate first formed redissolved on shaking. The sol thus formed was concentrated by boiling. In this way a sol containing 166.0 g. of ZrO_2 per litre could be prepared. This sol looked like glycerol and was highly viscous but contained a considerable amount of nitrate ion. As the sol prepared by the peptisation method is impure, we prepared our sols by the hydrolysis of zirconium nitrate solution and subjected it to dialysis. After dialysis lasting for one week at the ordinary temperature, the sol thus obtained was concentrated by boiling. By this method, a sol containing 402 g. ZrO_2 per litre was obtained. The purity of the sol, *i. e.*, ZrO_2/NO_3 was 2.5. In order to obtain a purer sol, this concentrated sol was diluted and subjected to hot dialysis and a sol containing 100.2 g. ZrO_2 per litre with a purity of 6.6 was obtained (sol A). The sol was clear in transmitted light but opalescent in reflected light and was slightly yellowish. On attempting to concentrate the sol further it becomes a jelly. It is evident, therefore, that if a sol of greater purity is to be prepared, its concentration cannot be as high as that of the sol A. Hence a portion of the sol A was diluted and subjected to dialysis. In this way, a sol containing 55.2 g. ZrO_2 per litre with a purity of 16.2 was obtained (sol B). This sol was colourless and was perfectly clear in both transmitted and reflected light. It was highly viscous and looked like glycerol. Any further attempt to get this sol in

a purer state by cold or hot dialysis leads to its gelation or the formation of a glassy mass.

The concentration of the sol was determined by evaporating in a platinum crucible a known volume of the sol to dryness and igniting it and weighing it as ZrO_2 . The amount of nitrate was estimated by treating it with Devarda's alloy and distilling off the ammonia and absorbing it by a standard solution of sulphuric acid.

Coagulation of the Sols by Electrolytes.

The sols being highly viscous and concentrated, the coagulation experiments have been carried on after diluting the sol 10 times with conductivity water. The sols are positively charged but could not be readily coagulated by even a saturated solution of potassium chloride. Hence the coagulation experiments were carried on with potassium bromate and potassium sulphate and the results are as follows:

TABLE I.

Coagulation time = 1 hour.

Sol A	Coagulating concentration of		Ratio.
	$KBrO_3(a)$.	$K_2SO_4(b)$.	
	0.1666 N	0.00516 N	32.2

TABLE II.

Coagulation time = 1 hour.

Sol B	Coagulating concentration of		Ratio.
	$KBrO_3(a)$.	$K_2SO_4(b)$.	
	0.06618 N	0.001666 N	39.6

The sols were stabilised by adding a solution of zirconium nitrate containing 1.0436 g. of the salt in 100 c. c. of the solution. 2 C. c. of this solution were added to 10 c. c. of the original sol. 10 C. c. of this mixture were diluted to 100 c. c. and this was used for the coagulation experiments and the results are recorded below.

TABLE III.

Coagulation time=1 hour.

	Coagulating concentration of		Ratio.
	KBrO ₃ (a).	K ₂ SO ₄ (b).	a/b
Sol A	0.1895 N	0.005249N	36.1
Sol B	0.08287N	0.00175N	47.8

Hence it appears that as the sol becomes impure and consequently more stable by the adsorption of Zr. ions, the ratio of the coagulating concentrations of mono- and bivalent electrolytes increases and this is in agreement with the results obtained with other hydroxide sols and follow the theoretical deduction of Chakravarti, Ghosh and Dhar (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1930, **34**, 330).

The influence of concentration of the sol on its coagulation has also been studied and the results are as follows :

TABLE IV.

Coagulating time=1 hour.

	Coagulating concentration of		Ratio.
	KBrO ₃ (a).	K ₂ SO ₄ (b).	a/b
Sol A	0.1723N	0.005416N	31.6
Sol B	0.06707N	0.001875N	36.5

It will be observed that with this sol the relations that the greater the concentration of the sol the greater is the amount of electrolyte necessary for coagulation irrespective of the valency of the coagulating ion, is applicable.

One interesting fact is that the coagulum in the case of the sol A which is less pure and less viscous than sol B appears white, whilst the coagulum obtained from the sol B which is purer and more viscous appears almost transparent and less white than that obtained in the case of sol A. Similar results are obtained with stannic hydroxide sols of different degrees of purity. It appears that the coagulated mass obtained from a highly hydrated and viscous sol is also associated with large quantities of water and appear transparent.

Viscosity of the Sols.

The viscosities of both the sols A and B at different concentrations were determined at 22° by Ostwald's viscosimeter and the results are recorded below :

TABLE V.

Viscosity of water at 22° = 0.009606.

Sol taken = 5 c.c.

Conc. of sol.	Sol A.		Sol B.	
	Density.	Viscosity.	Density.	Viscosity.
a (original)	1.104	0.23301	1.0568	1.71575
a/2	1.050	0.03326	1.028	0.20691
a/4	1.024	0.01806	1.012	0.04148
a/8	1.013	0.01192	1.0058	0.01973
a/16	1.0052	0.01072	1.0023	0.01344

The viscosity of these sols after the addition of 2 c.c. of zirconium nitrate solution containing 1.0436 g. of the salt in 100 c.c., to 10 c.c. of the original sols has also been determined and the results are compared with those obtained after adding 2 c.c. of water to 10 c.c. of the sols.

TABLE VI.

Conc. of sol.	Sol A.		
	Viscosity of pure sol.	Viscosity of sol mixed with $Zr(NO_3)_4$.	Viscosity of sol mixed with water.
a	0.23301	0.07566	0.08260
a/2	0.03326	0.02339	0.02590
a/4	0.01806	0.01738	0.01753
a/8	0.01192	...	...
a/16	0.01071	...	...
		Sol B.	
a	1.71575	0.99507	1.68259
a/2	0.20691	0.13784	0.18099
a/4	0.04148	0.02848	0.03859
a/8	0.01973	...	...
a/16	0.01344	...	...

Just as in the case of concentrated sols of ferric, chromic, and aluminium hydroxides, the viscosity of the highly concentrated zirconium hydroxide sol appreciably diminishes to a limiting value on repeating the viscosity measurements.

The surface tension of the sol was determined by the capillary rise method. We also attempted to measure the surface tension of the highly viscous sols by Du Nouy's method but no concordant results were obtained. The results obtained by the capillary rise method are recorded in Table VII. The specific conductivity of the sols was also determined and the results recorded in Table VIII.

TABLE VII.

Temperature = 22°.	
Sol.	Surface tension.
Sol A	70.2
Sol A + Zr(NO ₃) ₄ solution	70.61
Sol A/10	71.32
Sol B	71.66
Sol B + Zr(NO ₃) ₄ solution	71.14
Sol B/10	71.87
Water	72.22

TABLE VIII.

Sol.	Sp. cond. × 10 ⁻² .
Sol A	1.196
Sol A aged for 10 days	1.286
Sol A/10	0.274
Sol A/10 aged for 10 days	0.285
Sol B	0.425
Sol B aged for 10 days	0.452
Sol B/10	0.0898
Sol B/10 aged for 10 days	0.0949

It appears from the foregoing results on the measurements of the specific conductivity (Table VIII) that with time the specific conductivity increases probably because of the giving out of the adsorbed electrolyte by the colloid particles on ageing.

It has already been reported in a previous communication that when a highly concentrated sol of chromium hydroxide is allowed to dry up in the dark, a transparent residue is left which when mixed up with water passes back to a sol condition. Similar reversible behaviour is observed with zirconium hydroxide sol. When these concentrated sols of zirconium hydroxide are allowed to dry up in a desiccator over sulphuric acid in the dark, a transparent residue is left which swells up on the addition of water and passes into the sol state. When however, the sols are dried in the sun or on a water-bath, a part of the reversibility is lost. It, appears, therefore, that when the drying of the sol is rapid, the colloid particles get dehydrat-

ed and the reversibility disappears but when the sol is allowed to dry slowly in the dark, the dried mass is completely reversible and in this respect, zirconium hydroxide behaves like a lyophilic colloid.

The highly concentrated sols of zirconium hydroxide prepared by us are highly viscous. Sol B, which contains practically half the amount of zirconium hydroxide as present in sol A, is about 8 times more viscous than sol A. This is due to the fact that sol B is more pure (purity 16.2) than sol A (purity 6.6). Moreover, the viscosity of these sols is appreciably decreased on the addition of the peptising electrolyte, zirconium nitrate, which increases the charge on the colloid particles. Hence, these results conclusively prove that greater the purity of the sol and less the charge on the colloid particles, the greater is its viscosity.

From Table VI, it will be clear that the viscosity-concentration curve of a highly concentrated sol of zirconium hydroxide is steep and that this is more steep with the purer sol B than with A. Consequently, from the point of view of viscosity, the concentrated sols of zirconium hydroxide, like other hydroxide sols investigated in this laboratory behave as a typical lyophilic colloid. Moreover, the surface tension of zirconium hydroxide sol is appreciably less than that of water.

Summary.

1. By hydrolysing concentrated solutions of zirconium nitrate and by hot dialysis of the solution, highly concentrated sols of zirconium hydroxide containing 100.2 g. ZrO_2 i.e., 0.8172 g. mole ZrO_2 per litre with a purity 6.6 and 55.2 g. ZrO_2 i.e., 0.4502 g. mole ZrO_2 per litre with a purity of 16.2 have been obtained.
2. These concentrated sols are highly viscous and the greater the purity of the sol, the greater is its viscosity. The viscosity of these sols decreases when their electric charge is increased by the addition of zirconium nitrate solution. The viscosity-concentration curves of concentrated zirconium hydroxide sols are steep. The purer the sol the more steep the viscosity-concentration curve.
3. The ratio of the coagulating concentrations of potassium bromate and sulphate increases when zirconium nitrate is added to stabilise the sols.
4. The surface tension of concentrated sols of zirconium hydroxide is appreciably less than that of water.

5. The specific conductivity of the sols increases on ageing.
6. When these highly concentrated sols are allowed to dry slowly in the dark, the dry residue swells on adding water and passes into the sol again.

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